

In-Vitro Evaluation of Aqueous Leaf Extract of *Euphorbia hirta* L. on *Triticum aestivum* L.

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ABSTRACT

The present investigation carried out at Department of Botany, Jijamata College Bhende, during January 2025 to April 2025. This study investigated the effect of *E.hirta* leaf extract on the seed germination and seedling growth of Wheat (*Triticum aestivum* L.). The study aimed to determine whether aqueous leaf extracts of *Euphorbia hirta* L. promote or inhibit the germination and seedling growth of wheat. Aqueous leaf extracts of *Euphorbia hirta* L at different concentrations (Control,5%,10%,15% & 20%) were prepared and used for treatments. The study evaluated the impact of *E. hirta* leaf extract on wheat seedling, measuring germination percentage, root length and shoot length to assess its allelopathic effects. Germination percentage was noted on the 4th and 6th day of treatment. Seedling growth were measured on the 10th day of treatment. Standard sterilization procedures were followed using an autoclave to prevent contamination during experiment. The result showed that *E. hirta* leaf extract significantly inhibited seed germination and seedling growth of wheat. Higher concentration of *E. hirta* leaf extract causing greater reductions in seed germination and seedling growth. The finding suggested that leaf extract of *E. hirta* possesses allelopathic properties that may affect the growth and development of plant species.

Keywords: *Euphorbia hirta* L, seed germination, *Triticum aestivum* L, seedling growth.

INTRODUCTION

Euphorbia hirta is a small herbaceous plant, widely distributed throughout the tropics and subtropics of the world. *E.hirta* a widespread invasive weed, known for its allelopathic potential, influencing the growth of neigh-boring plants through the release of biochemical compounds. As a member of the Euphorbiaceae family, it thrives in diverse environments, including roadsides and agricultural fields. This study aimed to investigate the phyto-toxic effects of *E. hirta* aqueous leaf extract on *Triticum aestivum* (wheat) seed germination and seedling growth under in vitro conditions, providing insights into its potential impact on agricultural systems. The presence of weeds among crop plants can compromise harvest quality and increase production costs,

ultimately leading to high economic losses (Qureshi et al., 2021).

Triticum aestivum commonly known as bread wheat, is one of the world most widely cultivated and consumed staple crops. As a key food source, its productivity and quality are crucial for global food security. Wheat is a rabbi season food crops and the basic staple food of the world (Subhan, 2024). Today wheat is grown on more land area than any other commercial crops and continuous to be the most important food grain source for human. *Triticum aestivum L.* belonging to the family poaceae, is the most widely cultivated cereal crop after rice and maize (Sora et al., 2023; Ullah & Shakir, 2023). Historically I was among the first domesticated crop species (Tembo et al., 2025). Agronomically, *Triticum aestivum L.* is a major rabbi crop in countries like india and contributes significantly to the agricultural economy. However wheat production is influenced by various biotic and abiotic factors, including pests, diseases, drought, salinity and chemical exposure.

Aims and Objective:

The present study aims to investigate the in-vitro evaluation of aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta L.* extract on seed germination and seedling growth of *Triticum aestivum L.* Evaluate the effect of varying concentrations of *E.hirta L.* on wheat seed germination, investigate the impact on wheat seedling growth parameters (root length, shoot length).

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Collection of plant material:

E. hirta L. was collected from crop fields. Fresh leaves of the weed initially cleaned by distilled water to remove impurities and they were left to air dry at room temperature (26-30°C) for 4 days avoiding direct sunlight exposure, until all moisture was removed. Healthy, uniform seeds of wheat were purchased from the local market for present investigation.

Preparation of aqueous leaf extract:

10 gm air dried leaves of *E. hirta L.* was ground and mixed with 100ml distilled water. Aqueous leaf extracts are obtained as filtrate of mixture and final volume was adjusted to 100ml, this gave 100% aqueous leaf extracts. The extract was considered as stock solution and a series of different strengths 5%,10%,15% and 20% were prepared by dilution with distilled water.

Seed viability test:

A total 300 seeds of wheat were soaked in distilled water for 24 hrs. After 24 Hr, viable seed settled at the bottom, while some seeds floated on the surface called non-viable seed. Only viable seeds were collected for experiment and they are capable for germination under favorable conditions.

Fig. 1: ???

Sterilization of glassware:

Glassware and petri plates were cleaned, dried and sterilized using autoclave at 121 °C for 20 minutes under 15lb pressure. Sterilization ensured removal of microbial contamination during the experiment.

Application of treatment:

For each concentration, three set of petri plates were used. 10 viable seeds were placed in each petri plate on moist filter paper. Total germination sets were 5 (control, 5%,10%,15% & 20%). Seeds were allowed to germinate under laboratory conditions. Germination percentage was calculated on the 4th and 6th day of treatment. For the measurement of shoot and root length first we randomly select any seedling from each

petri plate and calculate its mean value after 10 days of germination

RESULTS

The present study revealed that the allelopathic influence of *E.hirta* L. on seed germination and seedling growth of *Triticum aestivum* L.

Seed Germination:

Mean germination percentage was calculated after 4th day and 6th day of treatment (Table No.1). After 6th day of germination higher concentration of extract i.e.15%&20% conc. showed the lowest germination percentage i.e.70%-80% as compared to control showed highest germination percentage i.e.100%.

Table 1: Effect of aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta* L. on seed germination of wheat

Sr. No	Concentration of aqueous leaf extract (V/V)	Mean Germination (%) (4 th day)	Mean Germination (%) (6 th day)
1	Control	93	100
2	5 %	90	93
3	10 %	83	90
4	15 %	80	83
5	20 %	76	80

Graph 1: Effect of aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta L.* on seed germination of wheat

Table 2: Effect of aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta L.* on root and shoot growth of wheat (After 10 days of germination)

Sr. No	Concentration of aqueous leaf extract (V/V)	Root Length (cm)	Shoot Length (cm)	Total Seedling Length (cm)
1	Control	5.5	12	17.5
2	5 %	5	11.1	16.1
3	10 %	3	8.3	11.3
4	15 %	2.5	5	7.5
5	20 %	2	1.2	3.2

Graph 2: Effect of aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta L.* on root and shoot growth of wheat (After 10 days of germination)

Seedling Growth:

Root length, shoot length and total seedling length were measured after 10 days of germination. 15% & 20% concentrations inhibit the root and shoot growth. Total seedling growth significantly reduced with higher concentration of extract. 3.2 cm seedling length was measured at 20% concentration and as compared to control the growth is 17.5 cm (Table No.2). That’s why higher concentration of *E.hirta L.*

resulted in decreased root and shoot growth, indicating inhibitory effects.

DISCUSSION

The result indicated *E.hirta L.* leaf extract has allelopathic compounds inhibiting wheat germination and seedling growth, potentially affecting crop productivity. The response varied depending on the

concentration of extract. at lower concentration a slight stimulation or minimal inhibition in germination percentage was observed compared to the control. However with increasing concentrations of the extract a significant reduction in germination percentage was recorded. Root length and shoot length were also affected. The control group (DW treatment) show maximum germination and healthy seedling growth. The result suggested that aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta L.* leaf possesses phytotoxic potential against wheat under laboratory conditions. However, further studies including biochemical analysis and field trials are necessary to confirm its practical application and ecological implication.

CONCLUSION

The present in-vitro study showed that the aqueous leaf extract of *E.hirta L.* significantly inhibit the germination and early seedling growth of *Triticum aestivum L.* To avoid economical loss weed residue like *E.hirta L.* should be collected from farm before the cultivation of new crop. Weed extract affected the germination parameter and physiological development, reflecting the severity of the weed in growth of an important indian crop. The role of weed in decrease plant productivity is highly responsible.

Conflict of interest

The authors declare no competing interests.

Data Availability Statement: Not applicable.

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